

Consecutive First Order Reactions : Hydrolysis of Dicarboxylic Esters*

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Kinetics of acid catalysed hydrolysis of malonic, succinic and adipic esters, in water, aqueous-ethanol and aqueous-dimethyl sulfoxide is reported. Swain's treatment has been utilised to separate the rate constants of the first and second steps of the reaction. The effective order of catalysts is hydrobromic acid > hydrochloric acid > trichloro-acetic acid > perchloric acid > mono chloro acetic acid, quite in consonance with the order for acyl-oxygen ($A_{AC}2$) mechanism. Increase in chain length increases the kinetic rate. Solvent influences are also discussed.

A study of acid catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl, isopropyl and diphenyl methyl acetate is reported in aqueous, aqueous-ethanol and aqueous-DMSO. $A_{AC}2$ mechanism is noticed in all the cases as shown by the rate data.

The work on acid catalysed hydrolysis of dicarboxylic esters is scanty except for the investigations carried out by Ingold¹ and hence it was thought worthwhile to study the acid catalysed hydrolysis of malonic, succinic and adipic esters in various solvent mixtures. The study also includes an investigation of branched chain esters in the alcoholic component mainly with a view to correlate mechanism and structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the esters used were of B.D.H. make and they were purified and distilled before use except diphenyl methyl acetate which was prepared by using the method described by Bunton². The compounds had the following physical constants.

Name of the esters	B.P.°C	M.P.°C
Diethyl malonate	198	—
Dimethyl succinate	196	—
Diethyl succinate	216	—
Diethyl adipate	246	—
Ethyl acetate	76	—
Isopropyl acetate	86.5	—
Diphenyl methyl acetate	—	39

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1. C. K. Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1375.

2. C. A. Bunton, J. N. E. Dey, R. H. Flowers, P. Sheel and J. L. Wood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 963.

DMSO was of B.D.H. (AR) grade and was used without further purification. Alcohol was of absolute grade. Sodium carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution and hydrochloric acid solutions required for kinetic studies were prepared using standard procedures³.

Preparation of Indicators : Screened indicator was prepared by mixing equal volumes of 0.1% solution of methylene blue and neutral red in absolute alcohol.

Analytical Method : The solution of the substrate and the catalyst in the mixed solvent after attaining the required temperature was mixed in a narrow mouthed stoppered bottle. 5 ml. aliquots of the reaction mixture were quenched in ice cold water at different intervals of time and titrated against the standard sodium hydroxide using screened indicator.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method employed to separate the rate constants of the two steps of the reaction,

is due to Swain^{4,5}. If r_1 and r_2 are the values of r corresponding to values of δ_1 and δ_2 which are determined by certain percentages of reaction, thus the ratio r_2/r_1 is equal to the ratio t_2/t_1 of the actual times of the reaction for these same percentages. A table of values of k versus t_2/t_1 is used to evaluate k following which a graph of k versus r for a certain values of δ will lead to value of k_1 . As $k = k_2/k_1$, now k_2 can be computed. Thus the separation of rate constants is carried out.

Catalyst influence and nature of the process : The catalytic order is hydrobromic acid > hydrochloric acid > trichloro acetic acid > perchloric acid > mono chloro acetic acid as shown by the following rate constants.

3. A. I. Vogel. "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", E.L.B.S. and Longmans Green, and Co. Ltd. (1961), pp. 234 and 241.
4. C. G. Swain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1696.
5. A. A. Frost and R. G. Pearson, "Kinetics and Mechanism", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1961, p. 170.

TABLE I

Compound	Medium	Catalyst	$(k \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1})$		Temp. 50°
			k_1	k_2	
Diethyl succinate	aqueous	HBr	189.5	93.08	
Diethyl succinate	aqueous	HCl	135.1	73.26	
Diethyl succinate	aqueous	CCl_3COOH	107.9	58.59	
Diethyl succinate	aqueous	$\text{CH}_2\text{Cl.COOH}$	28.04	13.93	
Diethyl succinate	aqueous	HClO_4	102.0	50.12	
Diethyl malonate	aqueous	HBr	121.5	57.02	
Diethyl malonate	aqueous	HCl	88.38	45.41	
Diethyl malonate	aqueous	$\text{CCl}_3\text{.COOH}$	70.25	37.98	
Diethyl malonate	aqueous	$\text{CH}_2\text{Cl.COOH}$	22.8	11.52	

The relative order is quite in consonance with the mechanism of AAC² mechanism postulated for acid catalysed hydrolytic reactions. Similar observation has been made by Bunton⁶.

Statistical factor : Ingold (loc. cit) derived an equation based on statistical requirements on the probability that a catalyst molecule or ion will form a complex with particular ester group will, for constitutional reasons be, different for each ester group.

The statistical relation between the velocities of any two steps is

$$K_m/K_n = \frac{m \sum V^m \sum V^{n-1}}{n \sum V^n \sum V^{m-1}}$$

In the special case of a dicarboxylic ester $s = 2$, $m = 1$ and $n = 2$, hence the equation reduces to the form

$$K_1/K_2 = \frac{(V_1 + V_2)^2}{2V_1V_2}$$

Further more for the symmetrical dicarboxylic ester,

$$V_1 = V_2$$

Thus

$$K_1/K_2 = 2$$

Invariably in all the cases as the table indicates the ratio is maintained nearly 2.

Structural influences : It will be noticed from the Table II that there is an increase in the kinetic rate as one proceeds from malonate to adipate which indicates that the larger the distance between carbethoxy groups the more facile the reaction is. Conjugate acid

6. C. A. Bunton, J. H. Crabtree and L. Robinson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1258.

formation is made facile when the deactivating carbethoxy groups are away from the site of the reaction. This is much against the trend noticed on the alkaline hydrolysis of the same group of esters where malonate is faster. The adipate is the least reactive as the requirements of the alkaline hydrolysis and acid catalysed reaction are entirely different.

TABLE II

Name of the esters	Solvent	Catalyst	$(k \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1})$		Temp. 50° K_1/K_2
			k_1	k_2	
Diethyl malonate	Aqueous	HBr	121.5	57.02	2.13
Diethyl malonate	Aqueous	HCl	88.38	45.41	1.95
Diethyl malonate	Aqueous	CH ₂ Cl.COOH	22.8	11.52	1.98
Diethyl malonate	Aqueous	CCl ₃ .COOH	70.25	37.98	1.85
Diethyl malonate	50% : 50% (v/v) alcohol-water	HBr	56.66	24.95	2.2
Diethyl malonate	50% : 50% (v/v) DMSO-water	HBr	108.5	52.78	2.05
Diethyl succinate	Aqueous	HBr	189.5	93.08	2.03
Diethyl succinate	Aqueous	HCl	135.1	73.26	1.84
Diethyl succinate	Aqueous	CH ₂ Cl.COOH	28.04	13.93	2.01
Diethyl succinate	Aqueous	CCl ₃ .COOH	107.9	58.59	1.84
Diethyl succinate	Aqueous	HClO ₄	102.0	50.12	2.07
Diethyl succinate	50% : 50% (v/v) alcohol-water	HBr	83.8	45.36	1.85
Diethyl succinate	50% : 50% (v/v) DMSO-water	HBr	152.7	74.89	2.04
Dimethyl succinate	Aqueous	HBr	158.0	77.53	2.03
Dimethyl succinate	50% : 50% (v/v) DMSO-water	HBr	163.9	79.03	2.074
Diethyl adipate	50% : 50% (v/v) alcohol-water	HBr	140.0	70.00	2.00
Diethyl adipate	50% : 50% (v/v) DMSO-water	HBr	370.8	184.1	2.014

A change in the alcoholic component as seen by the rate constant of dimethyl and diethyl succinate does not seem to bring out much difference in reactivity. Similar observations have been made in a study of mono carboxylic esters.

Change in solvent : As one proceeds from purely aqueous medium to 50%-50% (v/v) ethanol-water mixtures in the case of diethyl malonate there is retardation.

TABLE III

Compound	Solvent	Catalyst	$(k \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1})$		Temp. 50° K_1/K_2
			K_1	K_2	
Diethyl malonate	aqueous	HBr	121.5	57.02	
Diethyl malonate	50% : 50% (v/v) alcohol-water	HBr	56.66	24.95	
Diethyl malonate	50% : 50% (v/v) DMSO-water	HBr	108.5	52.78	

But with DMSO-water mixture there is acceleration almost nearing the rate in aqueous medium. This cannot be just rationalized on the basis of only dielectric constant especially the rate enhancement with DMSO. It appears that there is stabilization of the transition state by DMSO which seems to account for rate enhancement. Increase in rate is not so pronounced as observed in the case of anion reactions in aqueous DMSO⁷.

Acid hydrolysis of monocarboxylic esters

The rate constants of acid hydrolysis of ethyl, isopropyl and diphenyl methyl acetates are tabulated below :

TABLE IV

Compound	Solvent	Catalyst	Temp. 50° ($k \times 10^6 \text{min}^{-1}$)
Ethyl acetate	aqueous	HBr	256.4
Ethyl acetate	aqueous	HCl	229.5
Ethyl acetate	75% : 25% (v/v) alcohol-water	HBr	78.56
Ethyl acetate	75% : 25% (v/v) DMSO-water	HBr	195.7
Isopropyl acetate	aqueous	HBr	153.6
Isopropyl acetate	aqueous	HCl	127.8
Isopropyl acetate	75% : 25% (v/v) alcohol-water	HBr	33.09
Isopropyl acetate	75% : 25% (v/v) DMSO-water	HBr	107.2
Diphenyl methyl acetate	75% : 25% (v/v) alcohol-water	HBr	7.956
Diphenyl methyl acetate	75% : 25% (v/v) DMSO-water	HBr	15.80

As the table reveals, the order of reactivity is ethyl > isopropyl > diphenyl methyl. As found in the case of dicarboxylic esters the order of reactivity of the catalysts is HBr > HCl. It was expected that as branching of groups takes place in the alcoholic component, there may be a change of mechanism from AAC² to AAL¹. But the reactivity order seems to rule out the possibility of any change in mechanism even in the case of diphenyl methyl acetate where there is a possibility of a stable diphenyl methyl carbonium ion. Had there been a change in mechanism the diphenyl methyl acetate should hydrolyse faster than isopropyl acetate as found earlier with diphenyl methyl acetate and tertiary butyl acetate. The comparative low reactivity of diphenyl methyl acetate requires explanation. It is probably due to the lowering of the basicity of these esters by substitution of 2 phenyl groups on the alkyl carbon atom.

Hydrogen bonding as in (1) would reduce the basicity of the ester molecule and might facilitate acyl-oxygen fission. The '-I' effect of 2 phenyl groups while reducing the basicity of the ester would favour this hydrogen bonding.

This effect will reduce the standing concentration of the conjugate acid of the ester and hence the overall rate of reaction. In addition, protonation of the carboxylic ester may occur either on the ethereal or the carbonyl oxygen atom, giving conjugate acid II and III. Considerable evidence has accumulated to prove that acid catalysed alkyl-oxygen bond

fission gives a carbonium ion, by a reaction which should occur more easily in structure II where the positive charge is on the atom adjacent to the breaking bond. Acid hydrolysis with acyl-oxygen fission, where there is addition of water molecule to the acyl carbon atom, is much favoured by protonation of the acyl-oxygen atom as in III.

It is to be expected therefore that the relative ease of acyl or alkyl oxygen bond fission is to be governed not only by the tendency of the alkyl group to form a carbonium ion but also by the position of protonation. Substitution of two phenyl groups on the α alkyl carbon atom will reduce the basicity of both the oxygen atoms in an ester molecule, hence tending to reduce the rate of hydrolysis but the effect will be greater on the nearer ethereal oxygen atom. Structure III will be preferred to structure II and hence attack by water molecules on the acyl carbon takes place easily, with consequent acyl oxygen bond fission, despite the high stability of diphenyl methyl carbonium ion. Similar arguments have been advanced by Bunton and coworkers in their work in dioxan-water mixtures (*loc. cit.*).

As commented earlier with dicarboxylic esters, there is rate enhancement with DMSO water mixtures probably due to greater stabilization of the transition state.

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